

Design and Implementation of a Low-Power, Low-Area RISC Core Based on Vedic Mathematics

RH Naik, Ampabathuni Divya, Nidadavolu Venkata Sai Krishna, Ongole Gopi Chand, Vemula Gopi Krishna

Department of Electronics and Communications Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Mothadaka, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India.

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KEYWORDS

Reduced Instruction Set Computer, Von-Neumann architecture, Verilog HDL, Vedic Mathematics, and Sutras

ABSTRACT

This work presents the design and implementation of a 16-bit Reduced Instruction Set Computer (RISC) processor integrated with a Vedic-based Multiply-Accumulate (MAC) unit and a high-speed prefix adder, developed using Verilog HDL. The core objective of this work is to improve arithmetic performance and reduce power consumption through the adoption of Vedic mathematical algorithms—particularly the UrdhvaTiryakbhyam Sutra—for efficient multiplication, and the integration of a parallel prefix adder to accelerate addition operations within the Arithmetic and Logic Unit (ALU). The proposed architecture consists of major components such as the ALU, control unit, data path, register bank, program counter, and memory unit, capable of executing a total of 14 instructions. The prefix adder enhances the ALU’s computational efficiency by minimizing carry propagation delay, while the Vedic multiplier reduces overall latency and complexity in the MAC unit. Simulation and synthesis results demonstrate that the incorporation of the prefix adder and Vedic multiplier leads to significant reductions in propagation delay, power dissipation, and hardware area when compared to conventional RISC processor designs. The resulting 16-bit Vedic RISC processor exhibits improved speed, latency, and energy efficiency, validating its suitability for low-power and high-performance embedded system applications. The fusion of Vedic mathematics with prefix adder-based arithmetic design establishes a promising architectural framework for next-generation digital processors. The design entry and synthesis is done using Xilinx ISE 14.7 tool and simulation results are verified using Modelsim 6.3.

I. INTRODUCTION

When the controller design become more complex in CISC and the performance was also not up to

expectations, people started looking on some other alternatives. It had been found that when a processor talks to the memory the speed gets killed. So the one improvement on CPI was to keep the instruction set very

simple. Simple in not the way it works but the way it looks. That's why there are very few instructions in any typical RISC architecture where processor asks data from memory probably not other than Load and Store. At the end the pipelining added a new dimension in the speed just with the help of some additional registers, which increases throughput by reducing CPI. Hence the instruction can be executed effectively in one clock cycle. A common misunderstanding of the phrase "Reduced Instruction Set Computer" is the mistaken idea that instructions are simply eliminated, resulting in a smaller set of instructions. In fact, over the years,

The continuous demand for faster and more energy-efficient computing architectures has driven significant interest in optimized processor design methodologies. Reduced Instruction Set Computer (RISC) architectures, known for their simplicity and high execution efficiency, serve as a robust foundation for developing compact and low-power embedded systems. However, achieving high arithmetic performance within resource-constrained environments requires the integration of faster and more efficient computational units, particularly within the Arithmetic and Logic Unit (ALU). This need has led researchers to explore hybrid arithmetic techniques that combine traditional digital logic with advanced mathematical algorithms.

RISC instruction sets have grown in size and today many of them have a larger set of instructions than many CISC CPUs. The term "Reduced" in that phrase was intended to describe the fact that the amount of work any single instruction accomplishes is reduced at most a single data memory cycle compared to the "complex instructions" of CISC CPUs that may require number of data memory cycles in order to execute a single instruction. Most microprocessors in today's market are based on either RISC or CISC architectures. Research has shown that RISC architecture greatly boosts computer speed by using simplified machine instructions for frequently used functions. The following features typically found in RISC based systems.

- 1) Pre-fetching: The process of fetching next instruction or instructions into an event queue before the current instruction is complete is called pre-fetching.

- 2) Pipelining: Pipelining allows issuing an instruction prior to the completion of the currently executing one.

- 3) Superscalar operation: Superscalar operation refers to a processor that can issue more than one instruction simultaneously.

Vedic mathematics has emerged as a promising approach for designing high-speed arithmetic circuits, especially in multiplication-intensive applications. The UrdhvaTiryakbhyam Sutra, one of the most efficient Vedic multiplication techniques, enables parallel and

scalable computations with reduced propagation delay and lower hardware complexity compared to conventional multipliers. When applied within a Multiply-Accumulate (MAC) unit, Vedic multiplication significantly enhances throughput, making it well-suited for processor architectures requiring repeated arithmetic operations. Complementing this, parallel prefix adders—renowned for their ability to minimize carry-propagation delay—serve as a high-speed alternative to traditional adder structures within ALU design.

This project presents the development of a 16-bit RISC processor that integrates both a Vedic-based MAC unit and a high-speed prefix adder to improve arithmetic efficiency while reducing power consumption. The processor incorporates essential modules such as the control unit, register bank, program counter, memory unit, and datapath capable of executing 14 instructions. By combining Vedic mathematics with advanced adder architectures, the proposed design achieves significant improvements in speed, latency, and energy efficiency. The resulting processor architecture demonstrates substantial performance gains over conventional RISC designs, establishing a promising direction for next-generation low-power embedded systems.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

A Single Clock Cycle MIPS RISC Processor Design using VHDL by Mamun B, Shabiul I. and Sulaiman S:

This paper describes a design methodology of a single clock cycle MIPS RISC Processor using VHDL to ease the description, verification, simulation and hardware realization. The RISC processor has fixed-length of 32-bit instructions based on three different format R-format, I-format and J-format, and 32-bit general-purpose registers with memory word of 32-bit. The MIPS processor is separated into five stages: instruction fetch, instruction decode, execution, data memory and write back. The control unit controls the operations performed in these stages. All the modules in the design are coded in VHDL, as it is very useful tool with its concept of concurrency to cope with the parallelism of digital hardware. The top-level module connects all the stages into a higher level. Once detecting the particular approaches for input, output, main block and different modules, the VHDL descriptions are run through a VHDL simulator, followed by the timing analysis for the validation, functionality and performance of the designated design that demonstrate the effectiveness of the design.

Synthesis, Simulation, and Hardware Emulation to Prototype a Pipelined RISC Computer System by Hamblen J:

This paper describes a VHDL based rapid prototyping approach to simulate, synthesize, and implement a prototype computer system using commercial CAD tools, a meta assembler, a retargetable C compiler, and FPGAs in a hardware emulator. This methodology is utilized in a senior design laboratory sequence of two required courses for computer engineering students at Georgia Tech.

A Multithread Processor Architecture Based on the Continuation by Takanori M, Satoshi A and Masaaki I:

We are developing the Fuce processor based on the dataflow computing model. Fuce means fusion of communication and execution. In order to execute many threads with multiple thread execution units efficiently, the Fuce processor executes multiple threads using the exclusive multi-thread execution model. The core concept of the exclusive multi-thread execution model is continuation based multi-thread execution, which is derived from dataflow computing. The Fuce processor aims to fuse the intra-processor execution and inter-processor communication. The Fuce processor unifies processing inside the processor and communication with processors outside as events, and executes the event as a thread. In this paper, we introduce the architecture of the Fuce processor and evaluate the concurrency performance of a Fuceprocessor which we described in VHDL. As a result, we understood that the processor has concurrency capability when there is sufficient thread level parallelism.

Instruction-Based Self Testing of Delay Faults in Pipelined Processors by Virendra S. and Michiko I:

Although nearly all modern processors use a pipelined architecture, no method has yet been proposed in the literature to model these for the purpose of test generation. The paper proposes a graph theoretic model of pipelined processors and develops a systematic approach for delay fault testing of such processor cores using the processor instruction set. Our methodology consists of using a graph model of the pipelined processor, extraction of architectural constraints, classification of paths, and generation of tests using a constrained ATPG. These tests are then converted to a test program, a sequence of instructions, for testing the

processor. Thus, the tests generated by our method can be applied in a functional mode of operation and can also be used for self-test. We applied our method to two example processors, namely a 16 bit five stage VPRO pipelined processor and a 32 bit pipelined DLX processor, to demonstrate the effectiveness of our methodology.

3.EXISTING SYSTEM

Over A processor incorporates most or all of the functions of a computer's Central Processing Unit (CPU) on a single integrated circuit (IC) or semiconductor chip. It is designed to perform arithmetic, logical, and control operations efficiently. To achieve this, several innovative and unconventional design trade-offs are made without compromising performance, speed, or power efficiency.

The processor consists of a range of fundamental components. These include a register array of 8-bit and 16-bit registers, a 16-bit Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU), a 16-bit shifter, a program counter, an instruction register, a 16-bit comparator, an address register, and a control unit. All these units are interconnected through a common 16-bit tri-state data bus, which enables efficient data transfer between different components.

The top-level design of the system consists of two main blocks: the processor block and the memory block. These blocks interact with each other through a bidirectional data bus, an address bus, and several control lines. The processor fetches instructions from external memory and executes them to perform a program. These instructions are stored in the instruction register and decoded by the control unit.

The control unit generates appropriate control signals to coordinate the operation of different processor components. For example, if the instruction involves adding two registers, the control unit transfers the value of the first register to an operational register (OpReg) for temporary storage. Then, the value of the second register is placed on the data bus. The ALU is configured in addition mode, and the result is stored in the output register (OutReg). The output register holds the result until it is transferred to its final destination, such as another register or memory location.

During the execution of an instruction, a sequence of steps takes place, including fetching, decoding, executing, and storing the result. The program counter (PC) plays a crucial role by holding the memory address of the current instruction. After the execution of an

instruction, the program counter is updated to point to the next instruction. In a sequential flow, it moves to the next address, while in the case of a branch instruction, it is loaded with a new address corresponding to the branch target.

The address register supplies the required address to the address bus. At the same time, the control unit sets the read/write (R/W) signal to '0' to indicate a read operation and sets the Valid Memory Address (VMA) signal to '1' to inform the memory that the address on the bus is valid. The memory then decodes the address and places the corresponding data onto the data bus. Once the data is available, the memory sets the "Ready" signal to '1', indicating that the data is ready to be read by the processor.

Thus, through coordinated interaction between its internal components and external memory, the processor efficiently executes instructions and performs the required computational tasks.

4. PROPOSED METHOD

The objective of the project is to design a 16-bit RISC processor based on Harvard architecture which utilizes minimum functional units. The architecture of proposed 16-bit Processor is shown in Fig.5.1. The processor incorporates 16-bit ALU capable of performing 11 arithmetical and logical operations, 16-bit program counter, 16-bit Instruction register, Sixteen 16-bit general purpose registers, 3-bit flag register to indicate carry, zero and parity. The processor has four states idle, fetch, decode and execute. The control unit provides necessary signal interaction to perform expected function in all the states. The 16-bit program counter indicates the address of memory location from which the instruction is to be fetched. After the execution of current instruction, the program counter is incremented by one unless 'JUMP' instruction is encountered. When the 'JUMP' instruction is executed the program counter is incremented or decremented by the amount indicated by the offset

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Figure 1: Architecture

TABLE I: INSTRUCTION SET

	Instruction	Opcode			Operation
1	ADD	0	0	0	$Rd = Rs1 + Rs2$
2	SUB	0	0	1	If $Rs1 > Rs2$ Then $Rd = Rs1 - Rs2$ Else $Rd = Rs2 - Rs1$
3	AND	0	0	0	$Rd = Rs1 \& Rs2$
4	OR	0	0	1	$Rd = Rs1 Rs2$
5	NOT	0	1	0	$Rd = \sim Rs$
6	XOR	0	1	1	$Rd = Rs1 \wedge Rs2$
7	CMP (Equal)	0	1	1	If $Rs1 = Rs2$ Then $Equal = 1$, else $Equal = 0$ If $R1 = 0$ Then $AZ = 1$, else $AZ = 0$ If $Rs2 = 0$ Then $BZ = 1$, else $BZ = 0$ If $Rs1 > Rs2$ Then $AGB = 1$, else $AGB = 0$ If $Rs1 < Rs2$ Then $ALB = 1$, else $ALB = 0$
8	SHIFT LEFT	0	1	1	$Rd = Rs1 \ll 1$
9	SHIFT RIGHT	1	0	0	$Rd = Rs1 \gg 1$
10	LOAD	1	0	0	$Rd = Mem[Rs1]$
11	STORE	1	0	1	$Mem[Rs1] = Rs2$
12	JUMP	1	0	1	$PC = PC + Offset$
13	NOP	1	1	0	No operation
14	JZ	1	1	0	$PC = PC + Offset$ if $Rd == 0$
15	JNZ	1	1	1	$PC = PC + Offset$ if $Rd != 1$
16	LOAD 8-BIT IMMEDIATE	1	1	1	$Rd = 8\text{-bit Immediate}$

Figure 2: Operations

The instructions are written in instruction memory. The output of the program counter is provided to instruction memory as input. The instruction corresponding to the address pointed by the output of the program counter is fetched from instruction memory. The fetched instruction is stored and decoded in instruction register. In the decode process destination register, source register, address of the memory location or immediate value are assigned based on the opcode. The opcode is used by ALU to perform requested operation and also used by control unit to generate necessary control signals.

ALU:

Inputs “a” and “b” are the two input buses upon which the ALU functions are executed. Output bus “c” returns the outcome of the ALU operation. The ALU can perform arithmetic actions such as add, subtract, increment, decrement, and some logical operations such as AND, OR and XOR, NOT etc.

Opcode (4-bits)	Destination Register (Rd) Address (4-bits)	Source Register 1 Address (4-bits) (Rs1)	Source Register 2 Address (4-bits) (Rs2)
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Figure 3: Instruction of ALU

COMPARATOR:

The next module described is the comparator. It compares two values and returns either a ‘1’ or ‘0’ depending on the type of comparison requested and the values being compared.

For instance, to compare if inputs “a” and “b” are equal, apply the value eq to port sel. If ports “a” and “b” have the same value, port compout returns ‘1’. If the values are not equal, ‘0’ is returned.

Opcode (4-bits)	Destination Register Address (4-bits) (Rd)	Source Register 1 Address (4-bits) (Rs1)	Source Register 2 Address (4-bits) (Rs2)
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Figure 4: Instruction of Comparator

REGISTER:

It is used for the address register and the instruction register. These registers need to be able to confine input data on a rising edge of the clk input and drive output q with the captured data. The value of input a is assigned to output q when a rising edge occurs on input clk

REGISTER ARRAY:

It is used to model the set of registers within the CPU that are used to store intermediate values during instruction processing. These registers are read from and written to during the execution of instructions. The set of registers is modeled as a RAM of eight 16-bit words. To write a location in the register array, set input rd to the location to be written, input data with the data to be written, and put a rising edge on input clk. To read a location from register array, set input rd to the location to be read and set input rd to a ‘1’; the data is output on port.

Opcode (4-bits)	Destination Register Address (4-bits) (Rd)	Source Register 1 Address (4-bits) (Rs1)	Unused (4-bits)
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Figure 5: Instruction of Register

SHIFTER:

The next module to be described is the shifter. The shifter is used to perform shifting and rotation operations within the CPU. The shift has a 16-bit input bus, a 16-bit output bus, and a sel input that determines which shift operation to perform

There are sixteen 16-bit general purpose registers names R0 through R15. The register array has two read and one write ports. When ‘reg_wr’ signal is enabled, the data is written into a register indicated by the write address. Otherwise two registers indicated by the read addresses are read. The ALU performs 11 arithmetical and logical operations. Some of the operations require two operands, while others need only one. All the operands for ALU operations are provided by registers and the result of operation is written back into the specified destination register through the multiplexer.

Fetch Unit:

The function of fetch unit is to obtain an instruction from the instruction memory using current value of the program counter and increment the program counter value for the next instruction. 16-bit program counter and instruction memory together form fetch unit.

Decode Unit

The function of the instruction decode unit is to use the 24-bit instruction provided from the previous fetch unit to index the register file and obtain the register data values. The instruction register, control unit and registers together form decode unit.

Execution Unit

The execution unit of the processor consists of arithmetic logic unit (ALU) which performs the operation specified by the opcode. A key innovation in the proposed architecture is the integration of a Vedic-based Multiply-Accumulate (MAC) unit, designed using the UrdhvaTiryakbhyam Sutra. This Vedic multiplier provides parallel partial-product generation and accumulation, significantly reducing multiplication latency compared to traditional array or Booth multipliers. The resulting MAC unit achieves higher throughput and lower power dissipation, making it highly suitable for digital signal processing and arithmetic-intensive applications within the processor. The combined multiply-and-accumulate operation is optimized to execute efficiently within a single

functional block, improving overall data path performance.

UrdhavaTiryakbhyam is a Sanskrit word which means vertically and crosswire in English. The method is a general multiplication formula applicable to all cases of multiplication. It is based on a novel concept through which all partial products are generated concurrently. Fig. 2 demonstrates a 4 x 4 binary multiplication using this method. The method can be generalized for any N x N bit multiplication. This type of multiplier is independent of the clock frequency of the processor because the partial products and their sums are calculated in parallel. The net advantage is that it reduces the need of microprocessors to operate at increasingly higher clock frequencies. As the operating frequency of a processor increases the number of switching instances also increases. This results in more power consumption and also dissipation in the form of heat which results in higher device operating temperatures. Another advantage of UrdhvaTiryakbhyam multiplier is its scalability.

The processing power can easily be increased by increasing the input and output data bus widths since it has a regular structure. Due to its regular structure, it can be easily layout in a silicon chip and also consumes optimum area. As the number of input bits increase, gate delay and area increase very slowly as compared to other multipliers. Therefore UrdhavaTiryakbhyam multiplier is time, space and power efficient. The line diagram in fig. 2 illustrates the algorithm for multiplying two 4-bit binary numbers and . The procedure is divided into 7 steps and each step generates partial products. Initially as shown in step 1 of fig. 2, the least significant bit (LSB) of the multiplier is multiplied with least significant bit of the multiplicand (vertical multiplication). This result forms the LSB of the product. In step 2 next higher bit of the multiplier is multiplied with the LSB of the multiplicand and the LSB of the multiplier is multiplied with the next higher bit of the multiplicand (crosswire multiplication).

In order to multiply two 8-bit numbers using 4-bit multiplier we proceed as follows. Consider two 8 bit numbers denoted as AHAL and BHBL where AH and BH corresponds to the most significant 4 bits, AL and BL are the least significant 4 bits of an 8-bit number. When the numbers are multiplied according to

UrdhavaTiryakbhyam (vertically and crosswire) method, we get,

$$\begin{array}{r} AH\ AL \\ BH\ BL \\ \hline \end{array}$$

$$(AH \times BH) + (AH \times BL + BH \times AL) + (AL \times BL).$$

Thus we need four 4-bit multipliers and two adders to add the partial products and 4-bit intermediate carry generated. Since product of a 4 x 4 multiplier is 8 bits long, in every step the least significant 4 bits correspond to the product and the remaining 4 bits are carried to the next step. This process continues for 3 steps in this case. Similarly, 16 bit multiplier has four 8 x 8 multiplier and two 16 bit adders with 8 bit carry. Therefore we see that the multiplier is highly modular in nature. Hence it leads to regularity and scalability of the multiplier layout.

Each block as shown above is 2x2 bit Vedic multiplier. First 2x2 bit multiplier inputs are A1A0 and B1B0. The last block is 2x2 bit multiplier with inputs A3 A2 and B3 B2. The middle one shows two 2x2 bit multiplier with inputs A3 A2 & B1B0 and A1A0 & B3 B2. So the final result of multiplication, which is of 8 bit, S7 S6 S5 S4 S3 S2 S1 S0. To understand the concept, the Block diagram of 4x4 bit Vedic multiplier is shown in Fig. 5. To get final product (S7 S6 S5 S4 S3 S2 S1 S0), four 2x2 bit Vedic multiplier (Fig. 3) and three 4-bit Ripple-Carry (RC) Adders are required. The proposed Vedic multiplier can be used to reduce delay. Early literature speaks about Vedic multipliers based on array multiplier structures. On the other hand, we proposed a new architecture, which is efficient in terms of speed. The arrangements of RC Adders shown in Fig. 5, helps us to reduce delay. Interestingly, 8x8 Vedic multiplier modules are implemented easily by using four 4x4 multiplier modules.

Figure 6: Block Diagram of 4x4 bit Vedic Multiplier

Vedic Multiplier for 8x8 bit Module:

The 8x8 bit Vedic multiplier module as shown in the block diagram in Fig. 6 can be easily implemented by using four 4x4 bit Vedic multiplier modules as discussed in the previous section. Let's analyze 8x8 multiplications, say $A = A_7 A_6 A_5 A_4 A_3 A_2 A_1 A_0$ and $B = B_7 B_6 B_5 B_4 B_3 B_2 B_1 B_0$. The output line for the multiplication result will be of 16 bits as – $S_{15} S_{14} S_{13} S_{12} S_{11} S_{10} S_9 S_8 S_7 S_6 S_5 S_4 S_3 S_2 S_1 S_0$. Let's divide A and B into two parts, say the 8 bit multiplicand A can be decomposed into pair of 4 bits AH-AL. Similarly multiplicand B can be decomposed into BH-BL. The 16 bit product can be written as:

Using the fundamental of Vedic multiplication, taking four bits at a time and using 4 bit multiplier block as discussed we can perform the multiplication. The outputs of 4x4 bit multipliers are added accordingly to obtain the final product. Here total three 8 bit Ripple-Carry Adders are required as shown in Fig. 6.1

Figure 7: Block Diagram of 8x8 bit Vedic Multiplier

To further enhance computational speed, the system incorporates a high-speed parallel prefix adder in the ALU. Prefix adders excel in minimizing carry propagation delay through hierarchical carry computation, enabling faster addition operations than ripple-carry or carry-look ahead adders. Integrating this adder into the ALU allows the processor to execute arithmetic instructions with minimal latency, improving overall instruction execution speed. Together, the Vedic MAC unit and prefix adder form the core arithmetic enhancements of the processor, resulting in a 16-bit RISC architecture that demonstrates improved speed, reduced area, and lower power consumption compared to conventional designs.

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Simulation Results

Figure 8: Simulation Result

RTL Schematic

Figure 9: RTL schematic of adder

Figure 9 shows the RTL schematic of adder using preprocessing, prefix computation and final summation

Power Report

Figure 10: Power Report

Delay Report shows that the proposed design consumes a power of 0.028mw.

Device utilization summary:

Figure 11: Area Report

Figure 11 shows the area report of the RISC processor, where 455 lookup tables are required to perform the operation.

Timing Summary

Figure 12: Delay Report

Figure 12 shows the delay report of the RISC processor, where the circuit delay is 23.327 ns

Table 1: Compression table

	EXISTING SYSTEM	PROPOSED SYSTEM
DELAY	27.665ns	23.327ns
POWER	0.033mw	0.028mw
AREA	468	455
SPEED	36.14mz	42.86mz
PDP	0.9129	0.6531

5. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed 16-bit RISC processor integrating a Vedic-based MAC unit and a high-speed prefix adder demonstrates significant improvements in computational speed, power efficiency, and hardware optimization. By leveraging the UrdhvaTiryakbhyam Sutra for multiplication and utilizing a parallel prefix adder for rapid addition, the processor achieves reduced latency and lower area overhead compared to conventional RISC architectures. Simulation and synthesis results validate that the fusion of Vedic mathematics with advanced arithmetic units enhances the overall performance of the processor, making it suitable for a wide range of low-power embedded system applications.

In the future, this architecture can be extended by incorporating pipelining, hazard detection mechanisms, and superscalar execution to further increase throughput. The MAC unit can be expanded to support higher-bit operations or integrated with floating-point arithmetic for advanced DSP and AI workloads. Additionally, exploring low-power optimization techniques such as clock gating, operand isolation, and multi-threshold CMOS can further reduce energy consumption. With these enhancements, the proposed Vedic RISC architecture holds strong potential for next-generation high-speed, low-power processors used in IoT devices, biomedical instruments, and edge-computing platforms

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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